

COMPUTERIZED ACCOUNTING SYSTEM AND FINANCIAL REPORTING QUALITY OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The recent corrupt practices have raised lot of questions on the extent of reliability of the accounting system in both private and public sector. There have been series of criticism on the manual accounting system under which high level of misappropriation and manipulation exist. This study examined the relationship between computerized accounting system and financial reporting quality of manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. The cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for the study with a population of 115 manufacturing companies in South-South Nigeria. Data were retrieved using questionnaire as research instrument. Simple Bivariate analysis was used to analyze the data gathered with the aid of statistical package for social sciences software. The study revealed a strong positive significant relationship between sage accounting software and financial report reliability. The study also revealed a moderate significant relationship between sage accounting software and financial report timeliness. Also, the study revealed that there was a moderate significant relationship between quick-book accounting and financial reporting measures. The study concluded that computerized accounting system has positive significant relationship with financial reporting quality of manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. The study recommended that manufacturing firms should adopt computerized accounting system in order to trigger capacity for improved financial reporting reliability. Manufacturing firms should strengthen their database security mechanism as this is one of the major drivers in computerized system. The Manufacturing firms should continuously improve on the digital literacy of their staff as this will go a long way in enhancing the firms' financial report timeliness.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement in Information and Computer Technologies (ICTs) has transformed and become central to contemporary societies.

Presently, no aspect of human endeavor vis-a-vis sciences, arts, administration, crafts, commerce, medicine, accounting, etc. that does not make use of ICT in its day-to-day operation. ICT refers

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to “the acquisition, processing, storage and dissemination of vocal, pictorial, textual and numeric information by a micro-electronics-based combination of computing and telecommunications devices” (Kyeremeh, Prempeh, & Afful-Forson, 2019). ICT is a term that stresses the role of unified communications and the integration of telecommunications (Telephone lines and Wireless signals), computers as well as necessary enterprise software, middleware, storage and audiovisual systems, which enable users to access, store, transmit and manipulate information (Murray, 2011). Information technology comprises hardware and software, IT controls frameworks, and the human resources and skills required to develop, use and control these products and processes, to generate information to support decision making, operations, and organization strategies. It has transformed the way organizations perform their daily tasks (Lim, 2013).

Computers and other digital technologies have improved corporate relationships (Taiwo & Agwu, 2016); increased corporate and office reliability (Lim, 2013; Taiwo & Agwu, 2016); enabled research via collaboration (Lim, 2013); and, increased value creation across organizations (Taiwo & Agwu, 2016). It revolutionized the way organizations conduct their daily activities, providing vital information for planning, organizing, directing, leading, and controlling organizational activities (Ganyam & Ivungu, 2019). In addition, it also affected the manner accountants perform their duties enabling them to provide quality information for

improved decision-making (Dandago & Rufai, 2014). Such advancements led to the development of Computerized accounting systems (CAS). CAS is an accounting information system that processes financial transactions and events as per Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) to produce reports with the assistance of computers or automated devices (Kingi, 2013). In a Computerized accounting system, the framework of storage and processing of data is called the operating environment and consists of both hardware and software.

With a particular emphasis on accounting information systems, ICT led to the involvement of computers in performing accounting functions in organizations and the creation of Computerized accounting system. Nowadays any organization that wants to stay competitive and survive a turbulent environment must do so with due consideration of ICT (Akanbi & Adewoye, 2018).

Performance is often used to measure the success of a business entity. Financial reporting quality is a measure of the change in the state of an organization or the outcomes that result from management decisions and the execution of those decisions by members of the organisation (Carton & Hofer, 2006). Financial reporting quality is multidimensional in nature; however, despite the diversity of performance measures, the common categorization is to divide performance into financial and non-financial reporting quality (Combs, Crook, & Shook, 2005). Presently, CAS are been used to augment accounting functions (Taiwo, 2016). CAS has several benefits over manual systems such as

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speed, accuracy, reliability, backup, and flexibility, among others.

Today's business environment is very dynamic and undergoes rapid changes as a result of technological innovation, increased awareness and demands from customers. Business organizations, especially the manufacturing industry of the 21st century operates in a complex and competitive environment characterized by these changing conditions and highly unpredictable economic climate. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is at the centre of this global change curve. Laudon and Laudon, (1991) contend that managers cannot ignore Information Systems because they play a critical role in contemporary organization. They point out that the entire cash-flow of most fortune 500 companies is linked to Information System. The application of information and communication technology concepts, techniques, policies and implementation strategies to banking services has become a subject of fundamental importance and concerns to all manufacturing firms and indeed a prerequisite for local and global competitiveness. ICT directly affects how managers decide, how they plan and what products and services are offered in the manufacturing industry. It has continued to change the way manufacturing firms and their corporate relationships are organized worldwide and the variety of innovative devices available to enhance the speed and quality of service delivery. Financial reporting quality has also evolved over time, with a strong emphasis on transparency, comparability, and reliability. The adoption of

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by many countries has played a crucial role in promoting high-quality financial reporting, leading to greater consistency and comparability in financial reporting practices across diverse jurisdictions (FASB, 2015). This alignment promotes comparability, reliability, and transparency in financial reporting, thereby improving the credibility of financial statements. Some researchers have conducted general reviews on various facts surrounding the quality of financial reporting. Accounting standards convergence, accounting standards harmonization, economic crises, growth in disclosure requirements, and other factors have created an excessive focus on financial reporting. Also, the worldwide increase in accounting scandals in the early 21st century has pointed to weaknesses in financial reporting quality. The quality of financial reporting determines, and depends upon, the value of accounting reporting. Across the world, the demand has gone out for providing a clear and full definition of financial reporting quality. It is essential to provide high-quality financial reporting to influence users in making investments decisions, and to enhance market efficiency. Providing ideal methods for assessing the quality of financial reporting is another global demand. The higher the quality of financial reporting, the more significant are the benefits to be gained by investors and users of the financial reports. Moreover, financial reporting quality is a broad concept that does not just refer to financial information; it also includes other non-financial information that is useful for making decisions. This paper is a review of

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literature that focuses on what could influence the quality of financial reporting and how this quality could be assessed and measured.

According to the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), the Accounting Standard Board in the United Kingdom (ASB) [UK], and the Australia Accounting Standard Board (AASB), financial reporting quality represents financial statements that provide accurate and fair information about the underlying financial position and economic performance of an entity. Measures of financial reporting quality includes relevance, reliability, comparability, understandability, timeliness and faithful representation.

Manufacturing firms that overhaul the whole of their payment and delivery systems and apply ICT to their operations are likely to survive and prosper in the new millennium. Manufacturing firms are advised to re-examine their service and delivery systems in order to properly position themselves within the framework that dictates the dynamism of information and communication technology. The manufacturing industry in Nigeria has witnessed tremendous changes linked with the developments in ICT over the years. The quest for survival, global relevance, maintenance of existing market share and sustainable development has made exploitation of the many advantages of ICT through the use of automated devices imperative in the industry.

Statement of the Problem

Extant studies have been conducted in Nigeria on Accounting Information Systems (AIS) in

general; little research has specifically addressed its impact in the manufacturing sector. Akanbi and Adewoye (2018), Akesinro and Adetos (2016), Dandago and Rufai (2014), studied accounting information system and financial reporting quality. They concluded that there exist a positive significant relationship between accounting information systems and financial reporting quality. Agbim (2013) focused on the impact of accounting software on financial reporting quality of Deposit Money Banks and his study concluded on a negative significant relationship; Ironkwe and Nwaiwu (2018) studied the effect of computerized accounting on reliability of manufacturing companies. However their studies shows a negative significant relationships; Amahalu, Abiahu, and Obi (2017) sampled two Microfinance Banks (MFBs); Taiwo and Agwu (2016), Taiwo (2016) used a sample from Covenant University; Akande (2016) utilised a sample of Manufacturing companies ; and, Onalapo and Odetayo (2012) selected construction companies.

Also, the literature on the effect of Computerized accounting system (CAS) focuses on differential aspects of financial performance, such as the effect of CAS on payroll accounting (Alfred, 2014); CAS on external audit functions (Okoye & Oghoghomeh, 2011); and, CAS on service delivery (Okoye & Gbegi, 2012). This study therefore seeks to focus on measures of financial reporting quality, namely reliability, and timeliness in the firms. It is against this backdrop, the study seeks to examine the effect of a Computerized accounting system on the

financial reporting quality of manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of the Computerized accounting system on the financial reporting quality of manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. The study's specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the effect of sage accounting software on financial reporting reliability in Nigerian manufacturing firms.
2. Ascertain the effect of sage accounting software on financial reporting timeliness in Nigerian manufacturing firms.
3. Determine the effect of quickbook accounting software on financial reporting reliability in Nigerian manufacturing firms.
4. Ascertain the effect of quickbook accounting software on financial reporting timeliness in Nigerian manufacturing firms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

The study is anchored on the *diffusion of innovation* theory.

Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory

This theory was developed by E. M. Rogers, a communication theorist at the University of New Mexico, in 1962. According to Rogers (2003) innovation refers to the introduction of any "idea, practice or object that is perceived to be new". Innovation has two parts, the first is "the generation of an idea or invention" and the second is "the conversion of that new idea or invention into a business or other useful application" (Rogers, 2003). The theory identifies five characteristics of innovations

which affect their diffusion: *relative advantage* (the extent to which technology offers improvements over currently available tools), *compatibility* (its consistency with social practices and norms among its users), *complexity* (its ease of use or learning), *trialability* (the opportunity to try an innovation before committing to use it), and *observability* (the extent to which the technology's outputs and its gains are clear to see). These five factors influence the adoption of innovation to a different extent among five different adopter categories. The criterion for the categorization is *innovativeness*. This is defined as the degree to which an individual is relatively early in adopting a new idea than other members of a social system (Rogers & Shoemaker, 1971). The five categories are the innovators, often the first to try a new idea. The early adopters, often occupy leadership roles and embrace change as a part of life. Early majority, often jump the wagon after observing whether such innovation is worthwhile. The fourth is the late majority, they are sceptical of change. They often follow the majority of success stories. The final group is the laggards, i.e., they are the most conservative of all. They are often hesitant and even resistant to change. This theory is used as it points toward organizations' innovativeness and how it affects financial performance. Its role in the decision-making process and the general performance of the firms. Diffusion of innovation theory will guide this study to determine the effect that new ideas, invention or innovation have on the performance of firms generally and profitability in particular.

This theory is relevant to this study as it reveals how organizations can adopt and apply innovations in taking advantage of the available technologies to attain its corporate goals and improved on its performance.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Computerized Accounting System

Computerized accounting system (CAS) is a formal synergy between the computer, accounting and system. An accounting system is “a formal system for identifying, measuring, accumulating, analyzing, preparing, interpreting and communicating financial information of a particular entity to a particular group” (Ama, 2004). They emerged from advancements in information systems. Typical examples of information systems include management information system (MIS), transaction processing system (TPS), office automation system (OAS), decision support system (DSS), executive information system (EIS), expert system (ES) and accounting information system (AIS) (Al-Mamary, Shamsuddin, Hamid, & Aziati, 2014). The CAS assists in collecting and recording data and information regarding events that have an economic impact on organizations and facilitates its communication to internal and external stakeholders (Ganyam & Ivungu, 2019; Olusola, Olugbenga, Zacchaeus, & Oluwagbemiga, 2013). The fusion of ICT with accounting functions led to the creation of CAS. CAS is an accounting information system that processes financial transactions and events as per Generally Accepted Accounting Principles

(GAAP) to produce reports with the assistance of computers or automated devices (Kingi, 2013). CAS is the application of computer-based software to input, process, store, and output accounting information (Sugut, 2014). Amviko (2011) opined that CAS involves the computerization of accounting information systems established to facilitate managerial decision-making. Marivic (2009) describes computerized accounting as a method or scheme for recording, organizing, summarizing, analyzing, interpreting and communicating financial transactions of an entity to stakeholders via the use of computers and computer-based systems. This system uses specialized machines called calculators and computers in gathering information. Technically it is often referred to as Electronic Data Processing (EDP) System (Ama, 2004). They allow financial statements to be created from information stored in the database (Amahalu, Abiahu, & Obi, 2017).

Computer-based transaction system helps disseminate routine and critical business information speedily and efficiently (Lim, 2013). The use of IT applications changed various stakeholders' expectations to the need for access to more frequent and detailed accounting information and data, rather than periodical aggregated financial reports. Presently, CAS are responsible for analysing and monitoring the financial condition of companies, preparation of documents necessary for tax purposes, and providing information to support many other organizational functions such as production, marketing, human resource management, and strategic planning. The functions of CAS include

(Taiwo & Agwu, 2016): effective collection and storage of data; classification of financial information; summarizing and interpretation of financial information to external users.

Sage50 Accounting Software

Sage 50 is a set of accountancy and payroll products developed by Sage Group aimed at small and medium enterprises. Sage offer unrelated products under the Sage 50 name in different regions. The product name originally derives from the UK and Ireland version of the product where the number 50 indicated that it was aimed at companies with up to 50 employees. The products are described as cloud-connected, reflecting the remote working and online capabilities of the range (Symcox, 2022). Sage 50 Accounts has its origins in some of the earliest Sage products. A direct relative of the current product is the Sage Sterling range which became available in September 1989 as a replacement for Sage's Businesswise Accounts range (The Sage Plc, 1989). Sage Sterling was available for DOS, and in the early 1990s for Microsoft Windows. The product was re-branded as Sage Sterling +2, and in 1993 a version of the product.

Quick-Book Accounting Software

QuickBooks is an accounting software package developed and marketed by Intuit. First introduced in 1983, QuickBooks products are geared mainly toward small and medium-sized businesses and offer on-premises accounting applications as well as cloud-based versions that accept business payments, manage and pay bills, and payroll functions. The initial QuickBooks software did not function as a "double-entry"

accounting package. The initial release of QuickBooks was the DOS version that was based on the Quicken codebase. The Windows and Mac versions shared a different codebase that was based on In-House Accountant, which Intuit had acquired. The software was popular among small business owners who had no formal accounting training. As such, the software soon claimed up to 85 percent of the US small business accounting software market. It continued to command the vast majority of this market as of 2013(USA

TODAY, 2013). Professional accountants, however, were not satisfied with early versions of the system, citing poor security controls, such as no audit trail, as well as non-conformity with traditional accounting standards.

Intuit sought to bridge the gap with these accounting professionals, eventually providing full audit trail capabilities, double-entry accounting functions and increased functions. By 2000, Intuit had developed Basic and Pro versions of the software and, in 2003, started offering industry-specific versions, with workflow processes and reports designed for each of these business types along with terminology associated with the trades. Options now include versions for manufacturers, wholesalers, professional service firms, contractors, non-profit entities and retailers, in addition to one specifically designed for professional accounting firms who service multiple small business clients. In May 2002 Intuit launched QuickBooks Enterprise Solutions for medium-sized businesses.

In September 2005, QuickBooks had 74% of the market in the US (Businessweek, 2013). A June 19, 2008 Intuit Press Release said that as of March 2008, QuickBooks' share of retail units in the business accounting category reached 94.2 percent, according to NPD Group. It also says that more than 50,000 accountants, CPAs and independent business consultants are members of the QuickBooks Pro-Advisor program (Bonnie, 2015). By then Brad Smith was the new CEO, though former CEO Steve Bennett had nearly tripled Intuit revenue and quadrupled earnings in eight years (Brad, 2007).

In September 2015, Intuit released QuickBooks 2016 that contains several improvements to the existing ones and new features such as batch transaction, bill tracking, continuous feed label printer support, batch delete/void transactions etc (Accounting Today, 2015). In September 2016, Intuit released QuickBooks 2017 with several improvements like automated reports, smart search and improved viewing of report filters among other things (Accountex Report, 2016). In 2017, Intuit released QuickBooks 2018, adding features such as mobile inventory barcode scanning, multi-monitor support, search in the chart of accounts, etc. On September 17, 2018, Intuit announced the release of QuickBooks 2019 with some unique features requested by its users, including a history tracker for customer invoices, the ability to transfer credits between other jobs of the same customer, payroll adjustment feature, and more. On September 16, 2019, QuickBooks 2020 was launched with the aim to improve the reliability and experience of using the software.

All the desktop versions - Pro, Premier, Accountant, and Enterprise - include new features like the ability to add customer PO numbers in email subject lines, send batch invoices to customers, automatic payment reminders, collapse and expand columns, easy QuickBooks version update etc. On September 4, 2020, Intuit rolled out QuickBooks 2021 with improved payment process and automated features. All the desktop editions in this version have streamlined bank feeds, automated receipt management, rule-based customer groups, payment reminders, customized payment receipts, data level permissions, and batch delete sales orders (Ace Hosting, 2021).

Concept of Financial Report Quality

Accounting choices are made within the framework of GAAP. GAAP are the set of rules, practices, and conventions that describe what is an acceptable financial reporting for external stakeholders. The problem with many accounting choices is that there is no clear limit beyond which a choice is obviously illegal. Thus, a perfectly routine accounting decision such as expense estimation may be illegal if the estimated amount is extreme but perfectly legal if it is reasonable. Unfortunately, GAAP does not tell managers what specifically is normal and what is extreme and what is reasonable.

The reliance of external users on reported earnings as a fundamental variable for making decisions and recent corporate collapses mean that financial reporting quality has become a matter of great apprehension. For instance, using numbers, management may abuse "big bath" restructuring charges, premature revenue

recognition, reserves and write-offs of purchased in-process research and development (Johnson, 2019). These practices can threaten the credibility of financial reporting. There are concerns regarding financial reporting quality, which require factual and not fictional accounting to accentuate the importance of company accounts that are true and fair. The essence of this requirement is that companies must not distort, hide, fabricate and present, in whole or in part, deceitful financial reports.

Accrual – based financial reporting quality is motivated by the need for accounting adjustments and allocations made at the end of a given year for a number of reasons. Usually, accounting for routine exchange transactions does not result in accounting records being properly stated on the accrual basis to make adjusting and allocation entries at the end of the accounting period. The required adjustments are necessitated by the need to ensure that the financial accounts disclose a true picture of the transactions and operations of the organization, as well as comply with GAAP. While the key concept is that GAAP – based accounting is supposed to reflect, and not obscure true economic performance, GAAP may also be violated by actions that result or do not result in fraud (Okolie, 2014).

GAAP rules are often arbitrary, complicated, and occasionally misleading. This is characterized as a means of selective financial misrepresentation. Management, shareholders, auditors, and standard setters are motivated to support GAAP because selective misrepresentation of economic reality benefits them in some ways (Revsine,

2002). The thought that only GAAP defines what earnings or income is, means that if management is following GAAP, earnings are not being misrepresented. It is however clear that GAAP permits many accounting choices and requires much estimation through accruals, deferrals and allocations, thereby facilitating financial reporting quality; companies make innumerable operating and accounting choices and hence engage in some form of financial reporting quality.

Empirical Review

Masanja (2019) investigated ‘The impact of Computerized accounting system on the financial performance for selected private companies in Arusha, Tanzania’. The study adopted the descriptive and exploratory research design. The sample comprised of 61 employees in the accounting and financial department from 10 randomly selected private companies located in the Arusha region. The study is based on primary data; obtained from questionnaires. The data were analyzed using descriptive and Pearson correlation coefficients. The results showed that cost and management support were significant factors affecting the adoption of CAS. The correlation results showed a significant positive relationship between these two factors (cost and management support) and financial performance.

Akanbi and Adewoye (2018) investigated the ‘Effects of accounting information system adoption on the financial performance of the commercial manufacturing firms in Nigeria’. The study adopts the survey research design. The sample comprised 80 respondents randomly

selected from commercial manufacturing firms in the Lekki Peninsula Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The study relied on primary data from questionnaires; and secondary data from financial reports from 2007 to 2017. The results were analyzed using the linear regression technique. The results showed that Accounting Information System (AIS) adoption has a significant positive impact on gross profit margin, net operating profit, return on capital employed and return on total assets with $\alpha < 0.05$. Ironkwe and Nwaiwu (2018) examined the effect of the 'Accounting information system on financial and non-financial measures of companies in Nigeria'. The sample comprised 16 companies. The study relied on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were obtained from questionnaires; while, the secondary data was obtained from annual reports from 2011 to 2014. The data were analysed using multiple linear regression techniques. The results showed that the CAS had a positive significant effect on the financial and non-financial indicators of companies.

Borhan and Nafees (2018) conducted a study titled 'Effect of accounting information system on financial performance: A study of selected real estate companies in Jordan'. The study employed a survey research design. The study relied on primary data collected via questionnaires administered to 175 employees from 5 companies in Jordan. The data were analysed using the linear regression technique. The results revealed that there is a significant impact of CAS on financial performance.

Rehab (2018) undertook a study titled 'the impact of accounting information systems on financial performance: The context of Saudi's manufacturing companies'. The sample comprised 137 small and medium enterprises (Manufacturing companies) in Saudi Arabia. The study relied on primary data collected via questionnaires. The data were analyzed using smart partial least squares and validated the hypotheses. The results showed that AIS has a significant impact on financial performance; and, specifically on cost reduction, improving quality and effective decision making.

Borhan and Bader (2018) investigated 'The Impact of accounting information system on the profitability of Jordanian Manufacturing firms'. The study adopts the survey research design. The study relied on primary data collected through self-administered questionnaires from 206 employees in Jordanian manufacturing firms. The data were analyzed using the linear regression technique. The results showed that there is a significant impact of CAS on the profitability of manufacturing firms.

Peter, Kamau, and Ombui (2018) examined the 'Effects of Computerized accounting system on the performance of small medium enterprises: A case of the business community in Bomet County'. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The sample comprised 254 respondents in Bomet County using a stratified random sampling technique. The study relied on primary data; obtained from questionnaires administered to the respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The results

revealed that CAS (i.e., QuickBooks, sage, pastel and tally accounting systems) significantly improved Manufacturing companies' performance.

Amahalu, Abiahu, and Obi (2017) conducted a study titled 'Comparative analysis of Computerized accounting system and manual accounting system of quoted Microfinance Manufacturing firms (MFBs) in Nigeria'. The study adopted the ex-post facto research design. The sample comprised two Microfinance Manufacturing firms (MFBs). The study relied on secondary data obtained from annual reports and accounts from 2006 to 2015. The data were analysed using paired sample t-test. The results showed that CAS had a positive effect on ROA, NPM, and ROE.

Akesinro and Adetoso (2016) undertook a study titled 'The effects of Computerized accounting system on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria'. The study adopted a survey research design and a convenience sampling technique was used. The sample comprised 50 respondents from 3 Deposit Money Manufacturing firms (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study relied on primary data; which were analysed using correlation analysis. The results showed that a Computerized accounting system had a significant positive effect on a bank's profitability and customer patronage.

Taiwo and Agwu (2016) undertook a study titled 'Effect of ICT on accounting information system and financial performance'. The study used the survey research design. The study relied on primary data obtained from a sample of 20 staff in financial services and related accounting

departments at Covenant University. The data were analysed using Pearson's correlation via the aid of SPSS. The results showed a significant positive relationship between ICT and accounting system; and, a significant positive relationship between ICT and financial performance.

Preye, and Akon (2019) carried out a study on 'Effect of Computerized accounting system on the performance of financial institutions (A case study of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises)' using sage50 as a proxy for computerized accounting and return on equity as a measure of performance. The study adopted both exploratory and descriptive research designs. The study relied on primary data which was collected using structured questionnaires. The sample comprised 50 respondents (i.e., staff members) of manufacturing companies drawn using purposive and systematic sampling techniques. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results revealed that Sage50 accounting has a positive effect on performance from improved return on equity.

Adeola and Ayodele (2018) investigated the 'Effects of Computerized accounting system adoption on the profitability of the manufacturing firms in Nigeria'. The computerized accounting was proxied by sage50 accounting, while profitability was measured by return on equity. The study adopts the survey research design. The sample comprised 80 respondents randomly selected from manufacturing firms in the Lekki Peninsula Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The study relied on primary data from questionnaires; and

secondary data from financial reports from 2007 to 2017. The results were analyzed using the linear regression technique. The results showed that Computerized accounting system (CAS) adoption has a significant positive impact on return on equity, net operating profit, return on capital employed and return on total assets with $\alpha < 0.05$.

Benjamin and Nathan (2019) in their study 'Effect of Computerized accounting system on financial performance: A study of selected real estate companies in Nigeria. The study employed sage50 and ERP as the proxies of Computerized accounting system while return on Equity and return on assets were used as the measures of financial performance. The study employed a survey research design. The study relied on primary data collected via questionnaires administered to 125 employees from 5 companies in Nigeria. The data were analyzed using the linear regression technique. The results revealed that there is a significant impact of CAS on financial performance.

Michael (2020) investigated the issue of controls using quick-book accounting software and return on assets by assessing whether Manufacturing companies have effective internal controls and if such can prevent fraud. They concluded that the trace of internal control in place, Manufacturing companies need to work particularly on the authorization and personnel controls to avoid the incidence of fraud. It was

found that quick book accounting enhances effective control in the manufacturing industry and thereby reduces the opportunity for fraud occurrence. The researcher therefore recommended that manufacturing firms should adopt more of quick book accounting system in the order to aid the firm's control system.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is survey design. The reason is that the entire population cannot be studied and a survey is considered appropriate. The population for this study shall be all the manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria. However, due to the large population, the target population shall be forty (40) manufacturing firms across four (4) selected South-South States in Nigeria, namely: Akwa Ibom State, Rivers State, Cross River and Delta State. The sample size for the study was one hundred and forty-eight (148) respondents from the across the four states. The principal method of data collection adopted in this study was questionnaire and interviews. The demographic data was analyzed using frequency tables depicting percentages and frequency distributions for the sample characteristics. The univariate analysis of each variable was done using mean scores, standard deviation. While the bivariate analysis was carried out using the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient with the aid of statistical package for the social sciences.

DATA ANALYSIS

Relationship between Sage accounting software and Reliability

Table 1: Correlation Result for sage accounting software and reliability

		Sage	Reliability
Sage	Pearson Correlation	1	.786**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	133	133
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.786**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	133	133

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 1 illustrates the test for the first previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between sage accounting software and financial report reliability ($r = 0.786$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$);

Based on the result illustrated, the previous bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: there is a high significant relationship between sage accounting software and financial report reliability.

Relationship between Sage accounting software and financial report Timeliness

Table 2: Correlation Result for Sage accounting software and Timeliness

		Sage	Timeliness
Sage	Pearson Correlation	1	.543**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	133	133
Timeliness	Pearson Correlation	.543**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	133	133

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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 2 illustrates the test for the second previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between sage

Relationship between QuickBooks Accounting Software and Financial Report Reliability

Table 3: Correlation Result for QuickBooks accounting software and reliability

		QuickBooks	Reliability
QuickBooks	Pearson Correlation	1	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	133	133
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.562**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	133	133

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 3 illustrates the test for the third previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results show that:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between quickbooks accounting software and financial report reliability

($r = 0.562, p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

accounting software and financial report timeliness ($r = 0.543, p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous second bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a moderate significant relationship between sage accounting software and financial report timeliness.

Based on the results illustrated, the previous third bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a moderate significant relationship between quickbooks accounting software and financial report reliability.

Relationship between Quickbooks accounting software and financial report Timeliness

Table 4: Correlation Result for Quickbooks accounting software and Timeliness

		QuickBooks	Timeliness
QuickBooks	Pearson Correlation	1	.609**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	133	133
Timeliness	Pearson Correlation	.609**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	133	133

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output Version 21.0

Table 4 illustrates the test for the fourth previously postulated bivariate hypothetical statement. The results showed that:

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between quickbooks accounting software and financial report timeliness

($r = 0.609$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

Based on the results illustrated, the previous fourth bivariate null hypothetical statement is hereby rejected as the study finds that: There is a moderate significant relationship between quickbooks accounting software and financial report timeliness.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the analyses and findings above, the researcher thus concludes that Sage accounting software has high significant effect on financial report reliability and moderately influences timeliness; Sage accounting software influences timeliness; Quickbooks accounting software has

moderate significant effect on reliability and timeliness. Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Sage accounting software should be adopted by manufacturing firms in Nigeria as it highly influences financial reporting reliability.
2. Manufacturing firms should adopt sage accounting software as aid timely financial reporting.
3. Manufacturing firms can also adopt quickbook accounting software as it enhance both reliability and timeliness of financial report.

Contribution to Knowledge

Computerized accounting system positively impacts financial reporting through reliability and timeliness in the Nigerian manufacturing firms. Again, sage accounting software and quickbooks accounting software, positively influence the financial reporting via reliable and timely as indicated by the findings. Therefore,

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the main contribution of this study to knowledge is that computerized accounting system's proxy of sage accounting software and quickbooks

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